

Jeremy Abelson founded Irving Investors in 2009 after two successful exits in the digital media space. He combines his experience as an entrepreneur with institutional investing to find long-term sustainable investments in the public and private markets. He has contributed as an expert on Fox Business News, CNN, CNBC, The NYTimes, The WSJ and more. He also speaks at NYU, Columbia Business School and the NY Media Summit. Jeremy is originally from San Mateo, CA and graduated from The University of Michigan.

Irving Investors is a cross-sector growth fund. Irving employs a single name strategy and maximizes alpha generation by investing across the capital structure.

We attempt to identify the early stages of sustainable and transformative disruption and take a long-term approach to build significant concentrated exposure to it. We diversify within a theme with a varied mix of risk based on conviction, time in the cycle, cash management and risk management. Throughout the cycle, Irving will strategically invest in private companies, public companies, primary equity, secondary equity and a variety of credit instruments.

While we look for an early entry in a cycle, Irving will also maintain exposure deep into the maturity, evolution and value establishment of a portfolio company.

Irving was founded in 2009 as a dedicated public equities fund with a focus on internet names. The fund has since opportunistically expanded across sectors and asset classes. Irving now has three portfolios dedicated to public equities, corporate credit and alternatives and private investments.

The fund looks to form meaningful relationships with companies by offering its capital, expertise, and connections to promote growth and return on investment.

Irving has been involved in several successful private exits and is a trusted advisor and LP in Venture Capital funds.

The firm has offices in New York and Colorado.